

Am I Ecologically Literate for a Sustainable World?

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Individuals who comprehend the principles and boundaries of ecological systems, apply this knowledge to the development of sustainable communities, and aim to live in harmony with nature are considered ecologically literate. Therefore, in the initial stage, identifying students' existing levels of ecological literacy in order to foster awareness and consciousness plays a significant role in determining the subsequent steps to be taken based on the current situation. In this study, the ecological literacy levels of middle school students are examined in relation to various variables. The research was conducted using the survey model, one of the quantitative research methods. The sample group was determined through convenience sampling and consists of a total of 701 students enrolled in grades 5, 6, 7, and 8 at five public middle schools located in the western region of Türkiye during the 2024–2025 academic year. In the study, the “Ecological Literacy Attitude Scale” was used as the data collection instrument. The findings revealed that female students were more ecologically literate than male students. It was also determined that students whose parents had higher levels of education exhibited greater ecological literacy. Furthermore, students who had heard of the concept of ecological literacy and those who showed interest in ecological issues were found to be more ecologically literate compared to their peers. Within this framework, the ecological literacy levels of a specific group were identified according to their demographic characteristics.

Keywords: Ecological literacy; Environmental awareness; Secondary school students; Sustainability

1. Introduction

Literacy in the 21st century is regarded as a set of essential skills that individuals must possess in order to achieve self-actualization and for societies to remain competitive with others. The concept of reading, defined as a task of literacy, has influenced the emergence of various forms of literacy across different disciplines, thereby giving rise to multiple literacies (Sur, 2022). It is expected that individuals of the 21st century will acquire multiple literacies such as information, economic, geographical, cultural, media, legal, and technological literacy (Demir, 2021a). The knowledge and skills acquired through new forms of literacy provide significant benefits to both individuals and societies (Önal, 2010). Before examining the concept of ecological literacy, one of these new literacies, it is necessary to clarify two fundamental elements: ecology and literacy. Literacy is defined as the ability to read and write by using a system of symbolic language (Purwanti & Irawati, 2022). Ecology, on the other hand, is the field of study that addresses the relationships among humans, animals, and plants, as well as their interactions with each other and with their environment (Spurgeon, 2006). Within the axis of sustainability, reading, understanding, and writing nature constitutes the literate dimension of ecological science (Demir, 2021a). The term ecological literacy, composed of these two concepts, was first introduced by Risser in a speech at the Ecological Society of America in 1986, and later expanded by David Orr in 1992 (McBride et al., 2013; Boehnert, 2015). Ecological literacy refers to individuals' knowledge of ecosystems and the impacts of human activities on these systems, as well as their ability to apply this knowledge in their lives (Konoralp, 2024); the understanding of ecological principles and their application to environmental problems (Pouresmaieli et al., 2024); and the capacity to comprehend the natural systems that sustain life on Earth (Nugraha, 2015). As these definitions suggest, ecological literacy inherently encompasses the actions necessary to achieve sustainability and change (Eames & Aguayo, 2020).

Ecological literacy is the pedagogy of sustainable living. It enables individuals to develop new and diverse perspectives on life by reflecting on the possibilities of a "good life" (Pirili et al., 2019). In particular, adopting an ecology-based perspective allows educators to encourage students to critically engage with sustainability and to cultivate sustainable habits (Koyama & Watanabe, 2023). Indeed, individuals of the 21st century are expected to be ecologically literate, both as knowledgeable practitioners and lifelong learners (Demir, 2021a). An individual who comprehends the principles and boundaries of ecological systems, applies them to the development of sustainable communities, and aims to live in harmony with nature can be defined as ecologically literate (Pirili et al., 2019). Ecologically literate individuals possess knowledge of biodiversity, ecological processes, and sustainability. Such knowledge is essential for addressing ecological challenges and promoting sustainable development across communities. Consequently, ecological literacy enables individuals to make conscious and environmentally responsible decisions (Pouresmaieli et al., 2024).

The world we live in is increasingly deteriorating due to human impacts. Indeed, the fundamental reason for the emergence of the concept of ecological literacy is the ecological footprint left by humans on the planet. As the health of the Earth declines, the importance of ecological literacy grows (Tran Ho et al., 2023). Therefore, there is a pressing need to raise generations capable of finding solutions to existing problems. Cultivating environmentally conscious individuals has become essential to ensure the continuity of a livable environment (Yoleri, 2012; Çakır Arıca & Kağar, 2018; Demir & Ulukaya Öteleş, 2023). Early interaction with nature not only enhances individuals' interest and sensitivity toward the environment but also contributes to their intellectual, physical, and mental development. In particular, children who witness such contact during their upbringing acquire life lessons and develop a positive perspective toward all living beings (Çınar et al., 2023; Okyay et al., 2021). Experiential activities can foster students' awareness of their roles in global environmental issues while enabling them to address the root causes of unsustainable consumption, thereby encouraging both reflection and action (Aguilos et al., 2025). Hence, it is imperative to take measures and act in order to secure a sustainable future and leave a more livable world for future generations. Accordingly, cultivating ecologically literate individuals is of critical importance (Çakır Arıca & Kağar, 2018). To increase the number of ecologically literate individuals, the process that begins within the family must also be reinforced through education in schools (Acarlı, 2024).

Therefore, in order to foster ecological literacy among students, educational institutions must take comprehensive steps, beginning with the development of environmentally sensitive school policies. Considering the urgency of global environmental challenges, ecological literacy competencies are becoming an increasingly important focus for primary and secondary education in the 21st century. Specifically, ecological literacy encompasses students' comprehensive understanding of ecosystems, awareness of environmental issues, and the ability to engage in sustainable action (Palupi & Sarwanto, 2024). Thus, establishing knowledge and awareness of sustainable living among students aged 11–14 is crucial. At this stage, determining students' current levels of ecological literacy plays a significant role in enhancing their social responsibility and sensitivity from an early age, thereby fostering the awareness that small actions can lead to significant steps.

When studies on ecological literacy are examined, it is observed that research has been conducted on the development of ecological literacy among pre-service teachers (Makin, 2003; Kınacı, 2024); pre-service teachers' ecological literacy levels and perceptions (Zırhlı, 2025); teachers' processes of teaching ecological concepts (Puk & Behm, 2003; Magntorn, 2007); teachers' views on ecological literacy (Aydın et al., 2016; Okyay et al.; Demir, 2022); ecological literacy in education (Puk & Behm, 2003; Demir, 2021b); scale development studies related to ecological literacy (Demir & Oğuz Haçat, 2023; Koçoğlu et al., 2023); the development of ecological literacy skills in early childhood education (Özcan, 2022; Özer, 2023); the enhancement of ecological literacy among middle school students (Demir, 2021a; Palupi & Sarwanto, 2024); and the determination of middle school students' learning levels regarding ecological achievements (Atmaca, 2015). Emphasis has been placed on the importance of ecological literacy and the cultivation of ecologically literate individuals from an early age. In particular, recognizing and identifying skills and behaviors that begin to form during childhood

is crucial for sustainability. Based on this rationale, students who understand the importance of ecology can make decisions by considering the consequences of their actions, live in harmony with nature, and remain sensitive to the natural environment (Demir, 2021a: 11). In this regard, determining students' existing levels of ecological literacy in the initial stage, in order to foster awareness and consciousness, plays a significant role in guiding subsequent steps.

1.2. The Purpose of the Study

Based on the literature, the focus of this study is to determine the ecological literacy levels of students enrolled in public middle schools in Türkiye. In line with this aim, it can be stated that the study is original, as the ecological literacy levels identified through various variables are presented in a manner appropriate to the level of middle school students and easily comprehensible. Furthermore, the study is expected to raise awareness of ecological literacy among students and contribute to future research conducted by other scholars in similar fields. The research topic is considered original in that it will foster environmental awareness among the sample group of students and enhance their sensitivity to environmental issues. In addition, due to the limited number of studies on this subject, the present research is anticipated to provide valuable contributions to the academic community. Is there a significant difference in middle school students' ecological literacy attitudes across the following variables:

Gender,

Grade level,

Mother's education,

Father's education,

Type of residence,

Awareness of ecological literacy,

Participation in education at Science and Art Centers,

Interest in ecological topics,

Participation in nature-related activities within the last year (e.g., nature trips, tree planting),

Engagement in plant cultivation and animal care?

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

In this study, the survey model was employed to determine middle school students' attitudes toward ecological literacy. The survey design describes a situation that existed in the past or continues to exist in the present, as it is (Karasar, 2012). Since the aim was to examine middle school students' current ecological literacy attitudes and the factors influencing these attitudes, the survey model was deemed appropriate.

2.2. Research Sample

The sample of the study consists of 701 middle school students enrolled in five public middle schools located in the western region of Türkiye during the 2024–2025 academic year, selected through convenience sampling. Demographic information regarding the sample group is presented in Table 1 (gender, grade level, participation in education at Science and Art Centers, mother's and father's education levels) and Table 2 (type of residence, awareness of ecological literacy, interest in ecological topics, participation in nature-related activities within the last year such as nature trips and tree planting, and engagement in plant cultivation and animal care).

Table 1. Student and Parent Education Information Regarding the Sample Group

Gender	Grade level				Studying at the Science and Art Center		Education status of mother and father				
	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	8th grade	Yes	No	Primary School	Middle School	High School	Under graduate	Postgraduate
Female	71	97	127	56	68	282	67-53	94-96	115-84	63-96	12-22
Male	58	95	129	68	66	285	53-35	122-115	110-90	49-84	16-26
Total	129	192	256	124	134	567	120-88	216-211	225-174	112-180	28-48

Table 2. Demographic information on the sample group

Demographic information		n	%
The type of residence they live in	Apartment	506	72,2
	Detached house	195	27,8
Hearing about ecological literacy	Yes	154	22,0
	No	547	78,0
Interest in ecological issues	Interested	123	17,5
	Very little interested	257	36,7
	Not interested	321	45,8
Participation in nature activities in the last year	Yes	39	5,6
	Sometimes	320	45,6
	No	342	48,8
Plant growing situation	Yes	243	34,7
	No	458	65,3
Animal feeding status	Yes	271	38,7
	No	430	61,3

2.3. Data Collection Tools

In the study, the Demographic Information Form and the Ecological Literacy Attitude Scale were used as data collection instruments.

Demographic Information Form: In order to reveal the demographic characteristics of the sample group, the form included information on gender, grade level, participation in education at Science and Art Centers, mother's and father's education levels, type of residence, awareness of ecological literacy, interest in ecological topics, participation in nature-related activities within the last year (e.g., nature trips, tree planting), and engagement in plant cultivation and animal care.

Ecological Literacy Attitude Scale (ELAS): A review of the literature reveals that there are limited studies aimed at determining middle school students' attitudes toward ecological literacy, and the availability of scales addressing this issue is also restricted. Therefore, the "Ecological Literacy Attitude Scale," developed by Demir (2021a) in consultation with expert researchers, was employed in this study. The scale was designed to be appropriate for the level of middle school students and has established validity and reliability. The attitude scale consists of a total of 24 items, 15 positive and 9 negative. Careful attention is paid to scoring both positive and negative items, with the minimum possible score being 24 and the maximum 54.

The scale was constructed in a three-point Likert format, with a Cronbach's α internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.83. In this study, the Cronbach's α reliability coefficient calculated for the ELAS was 0.85. Thus, the ELAS can be considered a valid and reliable instrument.

2.4. Data Collection and Analysis

After obtaining the necessary permissions for the administration of the scale, data were collected from 701 voluntary students within one class hour (40 minutes) by the researchers, accompanied by the guidance counselors of the respective classes. The data collection process was carried out in May and June of 2025.

The collected data were transferred into the SPSS 26.0 software for analysis. Following data entry, the negative items were recoded. Subsequently, a normality distribution analysis was conducted to determine whether parametric or non-parametric tests should be applied. Skewness and kurtosis values, along with descriptive statistics, are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. ELAS normality test results

Descriptive Statistics Values						Kolmogorov-Smirnov (n>50)		
\bar{X}	Median	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis	Íst.	Sd	P
50,37	51,00	24	72	-,778	,827	,927	701	,172

As shown in Table 3, since the number of participants exceeded 30 ($n = 701$), the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test indicated that the data were normally distributed. In addition, the skewness and kurtosis values falling within the range of -1.96 to +1.96 confirmed the normal distribution of the data. In the statistical analyses, the level of significance was set at 0.05 (Can, 2014).

Independent samples t-tests were conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in students' total ecological literacy scores with respect to gender, type of residence, awareness of ecological literacy, participation in education at Science and Art Centers, and engagement in plant cultivation and animal care. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed for comparisons across grade level, mother's education level, father's education level, interest in ecological topics, and participation in hort h-related activities within the last year. To identify the source of the differences, Tukey's post-hoc test was utilized. Furthermore, effect sizes were calculated to determine the extent to which independent variables influenced the dependent variable, using Eta squared (η^2) for ANOVA and Cohen's d for the t-test (Can, 2014).

3. Findings

3.1. Findings on the Effect of Gender on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 3. Independent samples T-Test Results on the Effect of Gender on Ecological Literacy

Gender	N	\bar{X}	S	sd	t	p	Cohen's d
Female	351	50,71	4,62	699	1,872	0,04	0.05
Male	350	50,02	5,10				

As shown in Table 3, a significant difference was identified between the mean ecological literacy scores of female students and male students, in favor of female students [$t_{(699)} = 0,62$; $p < 0,05$]. Furthermore, the effect size of this difference was calculated as Cohen's $d = .05$, indicating that although female students were more ecologically literate than male students, the difference represented a small effect size.

3.2. Findings on the Effect of Grade Level on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 4. ANOVA Results on the Effect of Grade Level on Ecological Literacy

Group	N	\bar{X}	ss	Source of Variance	KT	sd	KO	F	p
5th grade (1st group)	129	49,92	5,48	Intergroup	87,803	3	29,268	1,229	,298
6th grade (2nd group)	192	50,82	4,30						
5th grade (3rd group)	256	50,44	4,88	Intragroup	16603,764	697	23,822		
6th grade (4th group)	124	49,96	5,05	Total	16691,566				

As shown in Table 4, no statistically significant difference was found among the arithmetic means of the grade levels [$F_{(3-697)}=1,229$; $p > .05$]. Therefore, it can be stated that the grade level variable does not have a significant effect on ecological literacy.

3.3. Findings on the Effect of Mother's Education Level on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 5. ANOVA Results on the Effect of Mother's Education Level on Ecological Literacy

Grup	N	\bar{X}	ss	Source of Variance	KT	sd	KO	F	p	Diff.	η^2
Elementary School (Group 1)	120	49,00	5,32	Intergroup	80,277	4	20,069	,841	,041	3,1-2	.00
Middle School (Group 2)	225	50,20	5,33								
High School (Group 3)	216	50,27	4,62	Intragroup	16611,289	696	23,867			4,3-2-1	
Bachelor's Degree (4th Group)	28	51,05	4,18								

Postgraduate (5th Group)	112	51,96	3,76	Total	16691, 566						
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As shown in Table 5, statistically significant differences were found among the arithmetic means of mother's education levels [$F_{(4-696)} = ,841$; $p < 0,05$]. The results indicated that the difference was in favor of students whose mothers had a high school education Group 3 compared to Grup 1 and Group 2. Similarly, the difference was in favor of students whose mothers had a bachelor's degree Group 4 compared to Group 3, Group 2, and Group 1. Furthermore, the difference was in favor of students whose mothers had a postgraduate degree Group 5 compared to Group 1 and Group 2. The effect size calculated from the test results ($\eta^2 = 0.05$) indicated that the differences were of small magnitude.

3.4. Findings on the Effect of Father's Education Level on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 6. ANOVA Results on the Effect of Father's Education Level on Ecological Literacy

Group	N	\bar{X}	ss	Source of Variance	KT	sd	KO	F	p	Diff.	η^2
Elementary School (Group 1)	88	49,30	,64	Intergroup	215,738	4	53,934	2,278	0,03	1,2-3 2,4 3,4-5	0,01
Middle School (Group 2)	211	50,00	,37								
High School (Group 3)	174	50,89	,30	Intragroup	16475,829	696	23,672				
Bachelor's Degree (4th Group)	180	51,03	,31								
Postgraduate (5th Group)	48	52,27	,66	Total	16691,566						

As shown in Table 6, statistically significant differences were found among the arithmetic means of father's education levels [$F_{(4-696)} = 2,278$; $p < 0,05$]. The results indicated that the difference was in favor of students whose fathers had a high school education Group 3 compared to Group 1 and Group 2. Similarly, the difference was in favor of students whose fathers had a bachelor's degree Group 4 compared to Group 2. Furthermore, the difference was in favor of students whose fathers had a postgraduate degree Group 5 compared to Group 3 and Group 4. The effect size calculated from the test results ($\eta^2 = 0.05$) indicated that the differences were of small magnitude.

3.5. Findings on the Effect of Type of Residence on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 7. Independent Samples T-Test Results on the Effect of Type of Residence on Ecological Literacy

Type of residence	N	\bar{X}	S	sd	t	p
Apartment	506	50,38	4,89	699	,109	,91
Detached house	195	50,33	4,85			

As shown in Table 8, no significant difference was found between the mean ecological literacy scores of students living in apartment buildings and those living in detached houses [$t_{(699)} = 0.91$; $p > 0.05$]. Therefore, it can be stated that the type of residence variable does not have a significant effect on ecological literacy.

3.6. Findings on the Effect of Awareness of Ecological Literacy on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 8. Independent Samples T-Test Results on the Effect of Awareness of Ecological Literacy on Ecological Literacy

The state of hearing the concept	N	\bar{X}	S	sd	t	p	Cohen' d
Yes	154	51,10	5,58	699	2,114	,035	0,18
No	547	50,16	4,65				

As shown in Table 8, a statistically significant difference was found between the mean ecological literacy scores of students who had heard of the concept of ecological literacy and those who had not, in favor of the former [$t_{(699)} = 0.35$; $p < 0.05$]. Moreover, the effect size of this difference was calculated as Cohen's $d = .18$, indicating that students who were familiar with the concept of ecological literacy demonstrated higher ecological literacy compared to those who were not, although the difference represented a small effect size.

3.7. Findings on the Effect of Receiving Education at Science and Art Centers on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 9. Independent Samples T-Test Results on The Effect of Receiving Education at Science and Art Centers on Ecological Literacy

Education status	N	\bar{X}	S	sd	t	p
No	567	50,25	4,71	699	1,34	0.17
Yes	134	50,88	5,52			

As shown in Table 9, no statistically significant difference was found between the mean ecological literacy scores of students who received education at Science and Art Centers and those who did not [$t_{(699)} = 1,34$; $p > 0.05$]. Therefore, it can be stated that the variable of receiving education at Science and Art Centers does not have a significant effect on ecological literacy.

3.8. Findings on the Effect of Interest in Ecological Topics on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 10. ANOVA Results on the Effect of Interest in Ecological Topics on Ecological Literacy

Group	N	\bar{X}	ss	Source of Variance	KT	sd	KO	F	p	Diff.	η^2
Interested (Group 1)	123	51,29	5,29	Intergroup	456,951	2	228,475	9,823	,00	1,2-3	,02
Slightly interested (Group 2)	257	51,01	3,98	Within Groups	16234,615	689	23,259				
Not interested (Group 3)	321	49,49	5,12	Total	16691,566						

As shown in Table 10, statistically significant differences were found among the arithmetic means of students' interest in ecological topics [$F_{(2-689)} = 9,823$; $p < 0.05$]. The results indicated that the difference was in favor of Group 1 compared to Group 2 and Group 3. Moreover, the effect size calculated from the test results ($\eta^2 = 0.05$) indicated that the differences were of small magnitude. These findings suggest that students with greater interest in ecological topics tend to demonstrate higher levels of ecological literacy.

3.9. Findings on the Effect of Participation in Nature-Related Activities within the Last Year on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 11. ANOVA Results on the Effect of Participation in Nature-Related Activities Within the Last Year on Ecological Literacy

Group	N	\bar{X}	ss	Source of Variance	KT	sd	KO	F	p
Participated (Group 1)	39	51,30	4,91	Intergroup	87,471	2	43,735	1,839	,16
Sometimes participated (Group 2)	320	50,02	5,19	Within Groups	16604,096	698	23,788		
Did not participate (Group 3)	342	50,58	4,55	Total	16691,566				

As shown in Table 11, no statistically significant difference was found among the arithmetic means of students' participation in nature-related activities within the last year [$F_{(2-698)} = 1,839$; $p > 0.05$]. Therefore, it can be stated that the variable of participation in nature-related activities within the last year does not have a significant effect on ecological literacy.

3.10. Findings on the Effect of Plant Cultivation and Animal Care on Students' Ecological Literacy

Table 12. Independent Samples T-Test Results on the Effect of Plant Cultivation and Animal Care on Ecological Literacy

Plant Growing	N	\bar{X}	S	sd	T	p
Yes	243	50,19	5,00	699	,684	,49
No	458	50,46	4,81			
Animal Feeding	N	\bar{X}	S	sd	T	p
Yes	271	50,00	4,51	699	,598	,11
No	430	50,60	5,09			

As shown in Table 12, no statistically significant difference was found between the mean ecological literacy scores of students who cultivated plants and those who did not [$t_{(699)} = ,684$; $p > 0.05$]. Similarly, no statistically significant difference was found between the mean ecological literacy scores of students who cared for animals and those who did not [$t_{(699)} = ,598$; $p > 0.05$].

4. Conclusion and Discussion

In conclusion, the study revealed that students' gender, parents' education level, awareness of the concept of ecological literacy, and interest in ecological issues influenced their ecological literacy levels. This study is expected to contribute to the literature by revealing the current state of ecological literacy among middle school students and by outlining the next steps to be taken based on the current situation in order to raise awareness and understanding. This shows that female students are more ecologically literate than male students. Studies have not found a relationship between gender and ecological literacy (Nadiroh et al., 2019). The findings show that students have greater ecological literacy as their parents' education levels increase. The development of ecologically literate individuals begins within the family institution and continues in educational institutions (Bilianska & Yaroshenko, 2020). Therefore, parents' awareness of environmental issues is expected to have a positive influence. In particular, parents who exhibit positive behaviors toward nature have been shown to positively affect their children's ecological literacy (Collado et al., 2015). Students who have heard of the concept of ecological literacy appear to be more ecologically literate than those who have not. As Hristidis (2008, cited in Özer, 2023) emphasized, those who have not heard of ecological literacy cannot recognize it, those who do not recognize it cannot appreciate it, and those who do not appreciate it are unlikely to engage in positive behaviors. In this context, students who are aware of and knowledgeable about the concept exhibit a more conscious approach and possess the characteristics of ecologically literate individuals. Promoting and developing ecological worldviews and literacy among students requires collaboration between schools, families, and the media (Kadamovna, 2025). The results of the research indicate that students with an interest in ecological topics exhibit greater ecological literacy than their peers who lack such interest. Ecological topics that stimulate children's interest can make the natural environment more meaningful and foster the development of ecological literacy (Häggström & Schmidt, 2020). Indeed, students need to establish a positive relationship with ecological issues and possess an intrinsic desire to make the world a better place (Ishaque et al., 2025). Individuals with greater

knowledge and awareness of ecology are more likely to transform this knowledge and awareness into environmental action (Yıldırım et al., 2025). Supporting this, Erdoğan (2011) found that an ecology-based summer nature education program increased students' environmental knowledge levels.

Individuals who comprehend the functioning principles and limits of ecological systems, utilize this knowledge for sustainable communities, and aim to live in harmony with nature are considered ecologically literate. In this context, knowledge and skills are regarded as crucial for initiating lifelong change, particularly among individuals aged 11–14. Therefore, identifying students' existing levels of ecological literacy in the first stage is essential for raising awareness and consciousness, and plays a significant role in determining subsequent steps. It was also determined that students whose parents had higher levels of education demonstrated greater ecological literacy. Furthermore, students who had heard of the concept of ecological literacy and those who expressed interest in ecological topics were found to be more ecologically literate compared to their peers. Within this scope, the ecological literacy levels of a specific group of students were identified according to their demographic characteristics.

To foster positive attitudes toward ecological literacy among students, learning outcomes should be integrated into curricula with practical and applicable examples. By emphasizing ecological literacy in educational institutions, its dissemination can be achieved through increased implementation of workshops, in-class and extracurricular activities, nature excursions, and family participation at all levels. In order to develop the components of ecological literacy, families, schools, and community members can play an active role in shaping students' attitudes and contribute to the process. The proportion of green spaces in schoolyards can be increased, and new schoolyard designs based on experiential learning can be developed. Similar studies can also be conducted with larger sample groups to strengthen the findings.

Acknowledgements

The authors received financial support for the research of this article. This research is funded by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye.

References

- Acarlı, D. S. (2024). *The place of ecological literacy in high school biology curriculum: The example of Turkey. In Cases on Collaborative Experiential Ecological Literacy for Education* (pp. 241-267). IGI Global.
- Aguilos, M., Leggett, Z., Jeffries, S., Lupek, M., & Ardon, M. (2025). University students' ecological footprint and lifestyle changes: Awareness vs. action. *Education Sciences*, 15(4), 432. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15040432>
- Aydın, M., Dündar, R. & Korkut, Ş. (2016). Teachers' perspectives on ecological literacy education in Turkey. *Abant İzzet Baysal University Faculty of Education Journal*, 16(USBES Özel Sayı II), 1160-1172.
- Bilianska, M., & Yaroshenko, O. (2020). Ability to foster schoolchildren's ecological literacy as a result of prospective biology teachers' professional training. *Problems of Education in the 21st century*, 78(6), 907-919. <https://doi.org/10.33225/pec/20.78.907>
- Boehnert, J. (2015). Ecological literacy in design education: A theoretical introduction. *Form Akademisk-Forskningstidsskrift for Design Og Designdidaktikk*, 8(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.7577/formakademisk.1405>
- Can, A. (2014). *SPSS ile bilimsel araştırma sürecinde nicel veri analizi* [Quantitative data analysis in the scientific research process with SPSS] (3. Edt). Pegem.

- Collado, S., Corraliza, J. A., Staats, H., & Ruiz, M. (2015). Effect of frequency and mode of contact with nature on children's self-reported ecological behaviors. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 41, 65-73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2014.11.001>
- Çakır Arıca, Ş., & Kağar, C. (2018). The key of leaving a life to the future generations: Ecological literacy. *Voice of Nature*, 1(2), 31-42.
- Çınar, G., Selman, T., Tuncer, T., Çakan, Ş., Ağgünlü, A., & Arslankılıç, M. (2023). Classroom teachers' perceptions of creating a democratic environment in classroom management. *International Academic Social Resources Journal*, 8(46), 2120-2130. <https://dx.doi.org/10.29228/ASRJOURNAL.67645>
- Demir, F. B. (2021a). *Investigation of the effect of the argumentation based science learning approach on the ecological literacy of 6th grade students* (Publication no. 666654) [Doctoral dissertation, Kastamonu University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center.
- Demir, F. B. (2021b). Eğitimde ekolojik okuryazarlık [Ecological literacy in education]. In E. Koçoğlu (Ed.), *Eğitimde Okuryazarlık Becerileri-II [Literacy Skills in Education-II]* (s.199-212). Pegem.
- Demir, F. B. (2022). Opinions and awareness of social studies teachers for ecological literacy. *E-International Journal of Educational Research*, 13(4), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.19160/e-ijer.1089887>
- Demir, F. B., & Oğuz, Haçat, S. (2023). Development scale of attitude to ecological literacy. *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 10(37), 24-38. <https://doi.org/10.29228/INESJOURNAL.73694>
- Demir, F. B., & Ulukaya Öteleş, Ü. (2023). Reflection of water literacy in the environmental education and climate change course teaching program. *Bulletin of Educational Studies*, 2(2), 50-57. <https://doi.org/10.61326/bes.v2i2.117>
- Eames, C., & Aguayo, C. (2020). Designing Mobile Learning with Education Outside the Classroom to Enhance Marine Ecological Literacy. *Teaching & Learning Research Initiative*, 2-20.
- Erdoğan, M. (2011). The effects of an ecology-based summer nature education program on primary school students' environmental knowledge, affective tendencies, and responsible behaviors. *Educational Sciences in Theory and Practice*, 11(4), 2223-2237.
- Hägström, M., & Schmidt, C. (2020) Enhancing children's literacy and ecological literacy through critical place-based pedagogy. *Environmental Education Research*, 26(12), 1729-1745. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2020.1812537>
- Ishaque, B., Paul, I. A., & Fatima, H. (2025). Exploring environmental education content and pedagogical skills for trainee teachers: A study on ecological literacy, environmental issues, and practical teaching approaches. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 13(1), 154-174. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2025.131009>
- Kadamovna, G. J. (2025). Raising an Ecological Worldview, Culture and Literacy in The Minds of Young People. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 5(04), 306-308. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijp/Volume05Issue04-81>
- Karasar, N. (2012). *Bilimsel araştırma yöntemi* [Scientific research method]. Nobel.
- Kınacı, M. K. (2024). *Modeling the relationship between ecological literacy levels and environmental education self-competences of social studies teacher candidates* (Publication no. 882965) [Doctoral dissertation, Fırat University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center.
- Koçoğlu E., Egüz S., Tösten R., Demir F. B., & Tekdal D. (2023). Perception of ecological literacy in education: a scale development study. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 11(3), 3-9. <https://doi.org/10.7575/Aiac.İjels.V.11n.3p.3>
- Konoralp, E. (2024). The role of forest schools on sustainable education and ecological literacy. *Socrates Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Studies*, 10(42), 60-78. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11617277>
- Koyama, D., & Watanabe, T. (2023). Why a dispositional view of ecological literacy is needed. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 28(5), 1108-1117. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2023.2198637>
- Magntorn, O. (2007). *Reading nature: Developing ecological literacy through teaching* [Doctoral dissertation, Linköping University].
- Makin, D. W. (2003). *The relationship between attaining ecological literacy and the development of a sense of community* [Master's dissertation, Lakehead University].
- Mcbride, B. B., Brewer, C. A., Berkowitz, A. R. & Borrie, W. T. (2013). Environmental literacy, ecological literacy, ecoliteracy: what do we mean and how did we get here?. *Ecosphere*, 4(5), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1890/ES13-00075.1>
- Nadiroh, N., Hasanah, U., & Zulfa, N. (2019). Behavioral geography: An ecoliteracy perspective and critical thinking skills in men and women. *Indonesian Journal of Geography*, 51(2), 114 - 122. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22146/ijg.36784>
- Nugraha, R. G. (2015). Meningkatkan ecoliteracy siswa sd melalui metode field-trip kegiatan ekonomi pada mata pelajaran ilmu pengetahuan sosial. *Jurnal Mimbar Sekolah Dasar*, 2(1), 60-72. <https://doi.org/10.53400/mimbar-sd.v2i1.1322>
- Okyay, Ö., Demir, Z. G., Sayın, A., & Özdemir, K. (2021). The effect of ecological literacy training on ecological awareness and environmental motivations of pre-school teachers. *Başkent University Journal of Education*, 8(1), 129-146.

- Önal, İ. (2010). Lifelong learning and literacy in process of historical change: A Turkish experience. *World of Information*, 11(1), 101-121. <https://doi.org/10.15612/BD.2010.258>
- Özcan, E. (2022). *Examination of children's ecological literacy levels: The case of Malatya* (Publication no. 770645) [Master's dissertation, Anadolu University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center.
- Özer, M. (2023). *The analysis of the applications that aim to develop ecological literacy skills in pre-school education: A case study* (Publication no. 806784) [Doctoral dissertation İnönü University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center.
- Palupi, D. H., & Sarwanto, K. (2024). Ecological literacy competence of primary school students in dagangan sub-district. *ISRG Journal of Art, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 307-301. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11635884>
- Pirili, M. U., Barbaros, F., Akdemir Veryeri, Z., Erdölek Kozal, Ö., Börü, P., Tunçer, S., Demir, M. & Uras, S. (2019). Ecological literacy seminars for everyone. *Meltem Izmir Mediterranean Academy Journal*, 5, 102-104. <https://doi.org/10.32325/iaad.2019.10>
- Pouresmaieli, M., Ataei, M., Qarahasanlou, A. N., & Barabadi, A. (2024). Building ecological literacy in mining communities: A sustainable development perspective. *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, 9, 100554. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscee.2023.100554>
- Puk, T. G. & Behm, D. (2003). The diluted curriculum: The role of government in developing ecological literacy as the first imperative in ontario secondary schools. *Canadian Journal of Environmental Education*, 8, 217-232.
- Purwanti, D. S., & Irawati, L. (2022). Problematika Implementasi Gerakan Literasi Sekolah pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia*, 3(2), 75-81. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v5i4.1209>
- Spurgeon, R. (2006). Ecology. (24. Edt). TÜBİTAK.
- Sur, E. (2022). A study on the concept of literacy and literacy studies in Turkey. *Journal of Ahmet Keleşoğlu Education Faculty*, 4(2), 445- 467. <https://doi.org/10.38151/akef.2022.27>
- Tran Ho, U., Lepage, B. A., & Fang, W. (2023). Environmental education in pre-school teacher training programs in Vietnam: Situations and challenges. *Journal of Early Childhood Teacher Education*, 44, 703-722. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10901027.2022.2136552>
- Yıldırım, M. S., Elkoca, A., Gökçay, G., Yılmaz, D. A., & Yıldız, M. (2025). The relationship between environmental literacy, ecological footprint awareness, and environmental behavior in adults. *BMC Public Health*, 25(1), 551. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-025-21340-3>
- Yoleri, S. (2012). Children and the environment: Creating environmental awareness among preschool children. *Buca Faculty of Education Journal*, 34, 100-111.
- Zırhlı, K. (2025). *Determination of ecological literacy levels and perceptions of social studies teacher candidates*. (Publication no. 933250) [Master's dissertation, Muş Alparslan University]. Council of Higher Education Thesis Center.